

SPECIAL COLLOQUIAL WORDS AND THEIR FUNCTIONS

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Abstract- Special colloquial words consist several vocabulary subgroups including: nonce-words, jargon, vulgarisms, dialectism, slang, professionalisms, archaisms. All these word stock known as common colloquial vocabulary which can be traced mostly in oral speech. Stylistic studies their function and difference between them. All of which have a certain property, characteristic of the layer on the whole, that is called an aspect.

Key words: professionalisms, slang, jargonisms, dialectisms, vulgarisms, colloquial-nonce words, poetical words, archaic words, literary layer, local color, aspect

Introduction

The major layers of English lexicology are the literary layer, the neutral layer and the colloquial layer. The aspect of the literary layer has bookish character and considered as a more or less stable whereas the aspect of colloquial layer has lively spoken character and they are unstable and fleeting. The following article defines its usage and appliance on various literary genres and analyses all functions and special features of special colloquial words from stylistic point of view and their appliance in literary works from literary point of view.

Main part

In stylistic it is essential to stress several vocabulary layers, such as neutral words, poetic words and special colloquial words which consist the main word stock of the language. They are interconnected and interplay yet interdependent. The literary and the colloquial layer contain a number of subgroups, all of which have a certain property, characteristic of the layer called an aspect. For this reason, the aspect of literary layer is its markedly bookish character, the aspect of colloquial layer is its lively spoken character. The former one is less stable, and the latter is unstable. The main features of neutral word is that it has universal character which allows unlimitedness in use.

The literary vocabulary consists of the following groups of words.

- Terms
- Poetical words
- Archaic words
- Foreignisms and barbarisms

- Literary nonce-words or Neologisms

Colloquial vocabulary falls into the following group:

- professionalisms
- slang
- jargonisms
- dialectisms
- vulgarisms
- colloquial-nonce words

The literary layer consists of the words are considered as legitimate members of English vocabulary, without local or dialectal character, whereas the colloquial layer is often limited and confined to a specific locality where it circulates.

The literary aspect of English vocabulary is used both in oral and written speech. Most literary words defined as neutral. However, there are certain groups of literary words whose bookish character permeates them with a distinct colouring. Hence, they are frequently called “learned words”. For example: emolument, joyance, gladsome, bellicose, judicial, etc. The common literary, neutral and common colloquial words are defined under the term: “standard English vocabulary”. Other groups are regarded as consequently special literary and special colloquial wordstock.

Neutral words that applied in everyday consumption both formal and informal way have polysemantic meaning and comprise main proportion in English vocabulary. In addition to this, neutral words can be used in any style of speech without causing a special stylistic affect applying both written and colloquial speech. Unlike all other group of words, the neutral words have no special stylistic colouring¹. For example:

Colloquial words	Neutral words	Literary words
kid	child	infant
daddy	father	parent
chap	fellow	associate

From these examples, one can notice some synonymic connection among these words but they have slight difference and cannot be easily replaced from one another. Common literary words are chiefly used in writing and in polished speech .

¹ Galperin I.R. Stylistics. – Moscow. Higher School. – 1997. p. 70-119.

The primary stylistic function of general literary words which appear in the speech of literary personages is to characterize the person as pompous and verbose. The speech of Mr. Micawber in "David Copperfield", said Mr. Micawber, "accidents will occur in the best-regulated families, and in families not regulated by that pervading influence which sanctifies while it enhances the – a – I would say, in short, by the influence of Woman, in the lofty character of Wife, they may be expected with confidence, and must be borne with philosophy".¹

Sometimes bookish wordiness is used to create a humorous effect. For example, in the following version of a famous fairy tale:

"Snow White".

Once there was a young princess who was not at all unpleasant to look at and had a temperament that may be found to be more pleasant than most other people's. Her nickname was Snow White, indicating of the discriminatory notions of associating pleasant or attractive qualities with light, and unpleasant or unattractive qualities with darkness. Thus, at an early age Snow White was an unwitting if fortunate target for this type of colorist thinking."

Special literary words may be grouped under the following divisions:

- Terms
- Foreignisms and barbarisms
- Archaic and obsolete/obsolescent words
- Poetic words
- Neologisms

Terms Learned words in English combine not only scientific terms, but also special terms in any branch of science, technique or art. A term – is a word (word-combination) denoting a scientific features. Terms may be divided into three main groups depending on the character of their etymology

- Terms formed from Greek, Latin, French, German or other foreign sources, e.g. Botany, anatomy, schedule (Greek); locomotive, chivalry, march, parliament, estate (Latin); facade, renaissance, retreat, maneuver, squad, coup d'etat, cliché (French); cobalt, zinc, quartz, sauerkraut (German).

Poetic words which have colourful with meaning can be applied in poetry and they are considered as monosemantic. They are insignificant in number and mostly archaic words which rarely used to produce an elevated effect of speech. The main function of poetic words is to create poetic atmosphere as a means of time and space in literary period². For example: Billow (wave), swain (lover),

² Berdiyeva N.R. International conference "Special colloquial words and their usage in "A clockwork Orange" by Anthony Burgess"

yeoman (peasant); lovesome (lovely), direful (terrible); list (listen), throw (believe); oft (often). Some poetic words often build by compounding. For example: young-eyed, rosy-fingered.

Archaic words - are those that have either entirely gone out of use or some of whose meaning have grown archaic. Archaic and poetic words are studied mostly by historical linguistics. Written works provide the best data for establishing the changes that happen to a language over time. For example, the following passage from Chaucer's *Canterbury Tales*, written in the English of the fourteenth century, has recognizable elements but is different enough from modern English to require a translation.

Barbarisms and foreignisms **Barbarisms** -are words of foreign origin which have not entirely become assimilated into the English language. Most of barbarisms have corresponding English synonyms: chic – stylish, bon mot – clever witty saying, ad finitum – to infinity; beau monde – high society. It is very important stylistically to distinguish between barbarisms and foreignisms. Barbarisms have already become facts of English language and are given in the bodies of dictionaries, while foreignisms though used for certain stylistic purposes do not belong to English vocabulary, nor are they registered by dictionaries. Foreignisms and barbarisms are used with various functions:

- to supply **local color**, i.e. introduce language elements that reflect the environment as a background to the narrative. By local color we also mean the devices used to describe the conditions of life the customs, the morals, and the manners of a given country at a given period. **Slang** is a language peculiar to particular group as a special and often secret vocabulary used by a class (thieves, beggars) and usually felt to be vulgar or inferior. The term slang is so broad that it includes many versions: cockney, public-house, commercial, military, parliamentary, journalistic and so on. For example: dame (teacher), ball up (make a mess), dust (drug), culture-vulture (sightseeing).

Slang phrases will ultimately go out of usage, but they allow individuals of a generation to develop their own style of talking with one another. It should be emphasized that slang is more suited in verbal or casual discussion; hence, slang is used infrequently in literature and is often saved for dialogue to convey a character's subculture or personality.

Literature Slang Examples

The slang employed in F. Scott Fitzgerald's *The Great Gatsby* reflects the historical period in which the narrative is set. The line contains an example of 1920s slang.

"He saw my adoration for his automobile. 'Isn't it lovely, old sport?' He leaped off to offer me a better perspective."³

Old sport" is a slang phrase used as a term of affection among upper-class gents.

The other type of special colloquial word considered as a **jargon** – occupation specific language used by people in a given profession to communicate with each other, as an example, in medicine the followings are used:

- Abrasion – cut or escape that typically isn't serious.
- Abscess – a tender fluid filled pocket that forms in tissue, usually due to infection.
- Acute – signifies a condition that begins abruptly and is sometimes severe but the duration is short.

Conclusion

Above mentioned word groups such as slangs, jargons and dialects has been used by several poets and writers according to the following reasons: to distinguish the character's unique way of speaking and illustrate their place of origin, cultural background or social class. Furthermore, it assists to recreate casual communication through colloquial dialogue, add authenticity.

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³ F. Scott Fitzgerald. The Great Gatsby .p.78